

VIEWS ABOUT SIGHT TRANSLATION AND SIMULTANEOUS INTERPRETATION

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Annotation. The article analyzes the importance of simultaneous translation among all types of interpretation. To do this, various aspects of this type of interpretation are considered, the characteristics of a simultaneous interpreter are assessed, and attention is also paid to possible difficulties that arise in the process of simultaneous interpreting.

Key words: simultaneous translation; oral translation; consecutive translation; simultaneous interpreter; translation; translation from sight; translation by ear.

Translation is critical to the life of modern society. The whole world is engulfed in the processes of information exchange and intercultural communications. There are cases when, due to misunderstandings between speakers of different languages, wars broke out and business relationships were destroyed. Translation is not only the selection of words in another language, but also the transfer of meaning, including subtext. In many cases, translation becomes especially significant.

In the modern world, foreign policy is of great importance for almost all countries. Often the leader of a country has to present his ideas to representatives of other countries of the world. Any inaccuracy in translation can lead to very serious consequences. Often the success of international negotiations depends on the quality of the translation.

Thus, understanding the essence of interpreting, as well as knowing the possible difficulties that a translator (for example, the Chinese language) may encounter in the process of interpreting will help to avoid professional mistakes in the future.

Translation is the transformation of a message in the source language into a message in the target language [2]. Accurate translation, by definition, is impossible because different languages are different both in grammatical structure and in the simple number of words, not to mention the differences in cultures[3]. Translation can be carried out both in written and oral form.

Written translation is a type of translation in which the original and the translation appear in the translation process in the form of fixed texts, which the translator can repeatedly refer to, deepening his understanding of the original and correcting selected translation options [1].

As for oral translation, the original and the translation appear in the translation process in an unfixed (oral) form, which means one the multiplicity of perception by the translator of pieces of the original text and the impossibility of subsequent comparison or change of the translation after it has been pronounced. Interpretation can be sequential – following the speaker’s delivery of his speech or some part of it - or simultaneous - when the translation occurs simultaneously with the delivery speaker speech.

Simultaneous translation can be considered the peak of an interpreter's skill, because it is very complex, and for many non-professionals it is completely mysterious or incomprehensible as a skill. Simultaneous translation is a responsible and rather difficult area in oral translation, because successful implementation of simultaneous translation requires special ones. And sometimes unique skills and abilities, as well as, of course, vast work experience.

In Russia, simultaneous interpretation appeared at the end of the 20th century and, in a sense, marked the end of the era of consecutive interpretation. Because simultaneous translation was logical and practical, it immediately became very popular. Technical progress also played a significant role in the development and popularization of simultaneous interpreting, which made it possible to create a proper technological base for simultaneous interpreters, which is a fundamental factor in organizing the work of a simultaneous interpreter at an international event. Simultaneous translation was available to a wide range of customers, had many positive characteristics, and therefore, for example, contributed to the development of international business [5]. When we say the phrase “simultaneous translation,” an association with responsibility and respectability immediately arises, and therefore representatives of the business community are naturally interested in using this type of translation. Thanks to simultaneous translation, the negotiation process became more intense, and the preparation time for various business projects was minimized. In addition, it is worth mentioning politics, because it was representatives of political circles who were the first to experience the convenience of simultaneous translation.

There are three types of simultaneous translation [4]:

- Simultaneous interpretation “by ear”. In this case, the text is perceived

It is communicated by a translator through headphones, the text arrives in blocks, parallel to the information. This type of simultaneous translation is the most common, but also the most difficult.

- Simultaneous “sight translation”. Such a translation can be carried out both with and without preliminary preparation. The text of the speaker's speech is provided to the translator in advance, based on the received materials, the translator performs the translation, and then, directly while the speaker is delivering the speech, makes the appropriate adjustments.

- Simultaneous reading of pre-translated text. In this case, the translator has a text that has been translated and prepared in advance. During translation, the translator can only read the text. Which has been fully prepared in advance, but be prepared to make minor changes if the speaker deviates from the original version of the speech.

In order for simultaneous translation to be successful, it is necessary to study the material in sufficient detail in advance and all available information that can be used in the speaker's speech; improvisation in the process of simultaneous translation should be minimal, taking into account the fact that during simultaneous translation the interpreter has practically no time to thinking about what was said, and there is no opportunity to clarify or repeat the information heard. This is the main difference between simultaneous and consecutive translation.

Simultaneous translation can be used at the following events: various conferences, seminars, forums, presentations. Behind the apparent simplicity lies a long and difficult preparation process, using the knowledge and skills of specialists from various fields of knowledge, including engineers, mathematicians, as well as directors, screenwriters, etc. Any negligence committed in the process of preparing for simultaneous translation can have a critical impact on the final result.

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